

NOTES

Optically Active Tertiary Alcohols from
 α -(+)-Ethyl -2- Methyl Valerate

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Some optically active tertiary alcohols containing two equal groups^{1,2} have been prepared by the interaction of α -(+)-Ethyl 2-methyl valerate and the appropriate Grignard complexes R-Mg-X, where R- is Me, Et, Pr (*n e i*), Bu (*n, i*, see *e tert*), phenyl and benzyl groups. Their optical rotations and the other data have been recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Optically active tertiary alcohols from α -(+)-Ethyl 2-methyl valerate.

Sr. No.	Name of the ter. Alcohol	B.P./ 15 mm. °C	Density d_4^{30}	Refractive index n^{30}	Sp. Rotation ($l = 1$) $[\alpha]_D^{30}$	Yield %
1.	1 : 1 dimethyl-1-ol-3-methyl pentane	60—65	0.8448	1.446	+2.93	70.0
2.	1 : 1 dimethyl-1-ol-3-methyl pentane	60—65	0.8279	1.452	+2.69	75.0
3.	1 : 1 di- <i>n</i> -propyl-1-ol-3-methyl pentane	90—95	0.9065	1.462	+2.39	66.0
4.	1 : 1 di- <i>iso</i> -propyl-1-ol-3-methyl pentane	110—120	0.8754	1.463	+1.79	62.0
5.	1 : 1 di- <i>n</i> -butyl-1-ol-3-methyl pentane	100—105	0.8698	1.462	+2.40	62.5
6.	1 : 1 di- <i>iso</i> -butyl-1-ol-3-methyl pentane	100—105	0.9168	1.451	+1.05	48.0
7.	1 : 1 di- <i>tert</i> -butyl-1-ol-3-methyl pentane	60—65	0.8654	1.429	+2.71	42.8
8.	1 : 1 di- <i>sec</i> -butyl-1-ol-3-methyl pentane	105—115	0.8356	1.438	+2.30	45.0
9.	1 : 1 di-phenyl-1-ol-3-methyl pentane	135—145	1.078	1.586	+3.46	65.0
10.	1 : 1 di-benzyl-1-ol-3-methyl pentane	190—195	1.078	1.674	+3.23	60.1

All the compounds described gave correct C, H, Analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -(+)-2-methyl valeric acid: The fusel oil contains α -(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol was distilled at 128–130° using a 16 cm. long fractionating column whereby pure α -(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol was obtained.

$$[[\alpha]_D^{30} - 4.69 (l = 1), d_4^{30} 0.8279, n^{30} 1.45]$$

1. J. Kenyon and A. Campbell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 436,
2. K. Thaker and I. Vasi, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 66.

α -(+)-1-bromo-2-methyl butane was obtained by the bromination of α -(-)-2-methylbutane-1-ol (320 gms.) with red phosphorus (20.71 gms) and liquid bromine (266.6 gms). The resulting α -(+)-1-bromo-2-methyl butane was distilled at 116–118°.

$$[[\alpha]_D^{30} + 1.52 \ (l = 1), \ d_4^{30} \ 1.258, \ n^{30} \ 1.4580]$$

α -(+)-1-bromo 2-methyl butane (151 gms., 1 mole) prepared as above in ether (250 ml.) was added during three hours to a flask containing dry magnesium (24.32 gms. \times 1 mole) and ether (250 ml.). The Grignard complex prepared as above was refluxed for one hour and dry carbon-dioxide gas was passed through it at -5 to 0° for 2 hr. It was decomposed by ammonium chloride solution (10%), extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was treated with sodium hydroxide solution (2 *N*). The α -(+)-2-methyl valeric acid was obtained by acidifying the sodium salt with hydrochloric acid (conc.), extracted with ether and on evaporation of the solvent the residual α -(+)-2-methyl valeric acid was obtained which was dried by anhy. magnesium sulphate and distilled at 97° to $100^\circ/15$ mm

$$[[\alpha]_D^{30} + 3.76 \ (l = 1) \ d_4^{30} \ 0.9636, \ n^{30} \ 1.4410. \quad \text{Yield : 70 gms. 60.34\%.}]$$

α -(+)-ethyl 2-methyl valerate : A mixture of α -(+)-2-methyl valeric acid (116 gm.), absolute ethanol (100 ml.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (5 ml) was refluxed for six to eight hours, the excess of ethanol was distilled off and the contents were poured in ice cold water, extracted with ether, and the ethereal extract washed with sodium carbonate solution (10%), and water, dried and on evaporation of the solvent the residual ester was purified by distillation at 140–145°.

$$[[\alpha]_D^{30} + 2.75 \ (l = 1), \ d_4^{30} \ 0.7954, \ n^{30} \ 1.429. \quad \text{Yield 108 gms., 75\%.}]$$

Optically active tertiary alcohols : α -(+)-ethyl-2-methyl valerate (0.5 *M*) dissolved in dry benzene (60 ml.) was added during one hour to a benzene solution of Grignard complex ((R.Mg.X) where R is Me, Et, Pr, (*n e i*), Bu (*n, i, sec, e tert*) phenyl and benzyl groups and the complex has been prepared in ether, the ethereal solution evaporated and the complex was taken in 60 ml. of benzene. On completion of the reaction, the benzene layer separated shaken successively with water and sodium carbonate solution (5%) and with water, dried, on evaporation of the solvent the residual optically active tertiary alcohols were obtained in respective cases, which were purified by distillation under vacuum.

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